

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE BOOK IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN THINKING, PHYSICAL, MENTAL AND SPIRITUAL HEALTH.

Azimova Dilfuza Yusufovna

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Senior teacher of the Department of Uzbek and Russian languages, head of the department of the Information Resource Center

People today are very busy and rarely spare time for reading. Because it is easier to immerse yourself in virtual life and have fun by grabbing the TV remote control, turning on the smartphone or opening the notebook.

However, people who read books have a higher chance of building a successful career, improving family relationships, they look younger than others and live longer. Therefore, I would recommend reading books for young people to spend their free time meaningfully.

Scientists have confirmed that regular reading is very beneficial for human health. Studies have shown that people who read regularly have a much lower risk of developing diseases such as Alzheimer's disease, depression, cardiovascular disease and even cancer.

It is important to note that even though e-books and other digital technologies are becoming more and more popular nowadays, paper books remain relevant due to the physical and psychological benefits they have on the reader.

Psychologists say, "Reading helps better than medicine."¹ Scottish researchers have found that a person suffering from depression can help themselves. The results of the study showed that reading literature helps better than medication².

In a 2013 experiment, two hundred people with varying degrees of depression took part. They were divided into groups and offered different treatment methods. The first group was treated with pills. The second one read self-help books.

It turned out that the group that was engaged in reading books achieved a much better result in treatment than the group that took antidepressants.

Reading books changes the way people think. At the same time, experts note that a comprehensive approach to the treatment of depression is optimal.

¹ «Ижод олами» журнали, 2018 йил, 5-сон

² <https://psyfactor.org/news/reading2.htm>

The results of the research are already being used in practice, in the form of so-called "literary interventions". Miranda McKerney, director of the Reading Agency, says: "There is a growing evidence base to show that books can really help with depression and other psychological problems. Doctors are now being encouraged to refer patients to the library as a way to treat them."³

People with psychological problems are given written instructions to visit their local library to read 30 approved texts. Each of the books has been rated as "effective" in helping with mental health problems and endorsed by the British Royal College of Physicians.

Why is it a better idea to choose a book instead of a movie?

You may have heard many times that reading a book is more beneficial than watching a movie. We know that with the help of good literature you can increase your vocabulary, change your focus and get rid of stress, develop creativity, but few people think about the useful side of the book from a psychological and scientific point of view. Why does the brain develop better when reading?

Even the most beautiful classic film does not require associative thinking from the viewer - the brain simply rests, because the film team decides everything for the viewer, and we just have to follow its footsteps.

"When watching a movie, all attention is focused on external factors and signals, your mind does not pay attention to what is happening on the screen. Usually, we start to "digest" the movie only after the credits roll. We observe the environment, draw some conclusions, absorb information, it becomes a part of us, and only then is it useful," says psychologist Alexander Shakhov⁴.

The process of reading a book is much slower, so the brain is more adapted to absorb new ideas. In terms of sharpening the mind and achieving knowledge efficiency, literature is more effective. Let's say we watched the feature film "War and Peace". On the one hand, it's a big story with costumes and fight scenes that keep us in awe. On the other hand, if we start reading the book, we will see the drama, values and ideas that Leo Tolstoy wants to convey. Since we have enough time, we can see again, understand what is happening, and then we can use this information in life.

During his experiment, Professor Ohad Landesman invited the participants to watch a short excerpt from the Western film "The Good, the Bad, the Ugly" and at the same

³ <https://varyag-domodedovo.ru/articles/chitat-knigi-ili-smotret-kino-cto-luchshe.html>

⁴ <https://dzen.ru/a/XV5RcsDc8gCtM2vv>

time measured the dynamics of the brain activity of the subjects using the film. The data obtained showed that certain visual images, dramatic actions and other components of the film had almost the same effect on all viewers. And the book gives every reader the opportunity to fantasize. The perception of the text is more individual, and it is unlikely that we will get two identical impressions from readers after reading⁵.

Reading teaches self-esteem and increases self-confidence. Communicating with you will be more interesting, because literacy and speech skills will increase, your worldview will expand, and your thoughts will deepen. Reading a book forces your brain to work at its maximum. Active brain activity has been proven to literally give you a second youth as the body ages slowly.

Researchers at Rush University in Chicago have reported that active intellectual activity helps keep brain tissue full and healthy⁶.

Neuropsychologist Professor Andre Aliman, author of the book "The Retired Brain", recommends regular mental exercises to maintain human health.

According to scientists from the University of California, brain activity is also stimulated by working on the Internet. Although online, the work of the human brain is focused on performing and solving several tasks at the same time. In particular, in the experiment, the parts of the human brain responsible for speech, reading, memory and vision are activated by reading a book.

Also, reading can bring up a whole range of emotions, and we all know that living them is essential. In the books, you can find answers to many interesting questions that will make you think about the meaning of life, love, friendship. We evaluate the actions of the characters, try the situations for ourselves, as if we live a literary life with them. And, of course, we will have the opportunity to learn from someone else's experience. As the famous French author Frédéric Begheder said: "Books are a good way to talk to someone who can't talk⁷".

When you read works of different genres, you will come across words that are not usually used in everyday speech. If a word is unfamiliar to you, you don't need to look up its definition in a dictionary. Sometimes the meaning of a term can be understood from the context of the text.

⁵ <https://dzen.ru/a/XV5RcsDc8gCtM2vv>

⁶ <https://dzen.ru/a/XV5RcsDc8gCtM2vv>

⁷ <https://mybook.ru/author/frederik-begheder/francuzskij-roman/citations/163208/>

Reading not only increases vocabulary, but also general literacy, as well as intelligence. This is especially important for children. According to the results of the study, a child's developed reading skills at an early age lead to a higher intelligence later on.

Reading not only improves literacy, but also improves your speaking skills - you will be able to express your thoughts clearly, clearly and beautifully. After reading a few classics, your storytelling skills will improve. You make a great impression on people and become an interesting conversationalist.

Reading makes us more confident. Reading books helps to broaden your outlook and increase your knowledge about the world. We learn about different cultures, historical events, scientific theories and other aspects of life.

In today's world, stress relief is a major concern of many people. Scientific experiments have shown that reading can reduce anxiety and depression levels.

The book distracts from everyday problems and creates a positive emotional background. Reading activates the brain and develops skills such as memory, attention, perception, imagination, logic, thinking.

Reading a book before bed helps to relax physically and mentally.

Today, a long-term study of people aged 50 and over found that people who read 30 minutes a day lived an average of 2 years longer than those who didn't.

REFERENCES:

1. Ritchie S.J., Bates T.C., Plomin R. does learning to read improve intelligence? Multivariate analysis of identical twins aged 7 to 16 years. January-February 2015; 86(1):23-36
2. Kidd D. C., Castano E. reading literary fiction improves theory of mind. Science. 2013 Oct 18; 342 (6156): 377-80.
3. Baron, N. S. what do we know How digital technology is disrupting learning and remembering. Journal of Pragmatics, 2021, 175, 27-37
5. Friedland R. P., Fritsch T., Smith K. A., Koss E, Lemer A.J. "About Alzheimer's Disease" March 13, 2001; 98(6):3440-5

6. Falbe J, Davison KK, Franckler RL, Ganter C, Gortmaker S. L., Smith L., Land T., Taveras E.M. Sleep duration, rest and sleep environment screens. *Pediatrics*. 2015 Feb; 135(2):367-75.
7. Bavishi A., Slad M.D., Levy B.R. A chapter a day: the link between reading and longevity. *Soc Med*. 2016 You; 164: 44-48.
8. *«Ижод олами» журнали, 2018 йил, 5-сон*
9. Фредерик Бегбедер, «книги — хороший способ поговорить с тем, с кем разговор невозможен».
9. <https://eksmo.ru/articles/chem-polezno-chtenie-ID15485892/>
10. <https://varyag-domodedovo.ru/articles/chitat-knigi-ili-smotret-kino-chtoluchshe.html>
11. <https://dzen.ru/a/XV5RcsDc8gCtM2vv>